

Synthesis of Benzofuopyranones, Naphthofuopyranones, Benzofuopyridinones and Naphthofuopyridinones. Part-II

K. V. WALAVALKAR, ANIL SINGH, C. N. ARVINDAKSHAN and U. C. MASHELKAR*

Organic Research Laboratory, Patkar College, Goregaon (West), Bombay-400 062

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The literature of benzofuopyranones, naphthofuopyranones, benzofuopyridinones and naphthofuopyridinones is scanty. These compounds have not been much studied except antilipedemic properties of some benzofuro[3,4-*b*]pyranones¹. These compounds however could be looked upon as compounds with potential medicinal activity.

In our earlier communication² we have reported synthesis of some benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridinones, naphtho[2',3':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyridinones and naphtho[1',2':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyridinones by action of DMF/POCl₃ on 2-carboxybenzofuro-3-acetic acid (1a), 2-carboxynaphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-3-acetic acid (1b) and 2-carboxynaphtho[1,2-*b*]furan-3-acetic acid (1c). In this paper we report the synthesis of 3-methylbenzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyran-1-one (3a), 3-methylnaphtho[2',3':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyran-1-one (3b) and 3-methylnaphtho[1',2':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyran-1-one (3c) by heating the respective acids (1a–c) with acetic anhydride and pyridine, with small amounts of the 4-carboxy derivatives (4a–c). Treatment of 1a–c with Ac₂O/Py at room temperature gave 4-acetyl benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyran-1,3-dione (2a), 4-acetylnaphtho[2',3':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyran-1,3-dione (2b) and 4-acetylnaphtho[1',2':5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyran-1,3-dione (2c) respectively, indicating that 2a–c were the intermediates in converting 1a–c to 3a–c (Table 1). Compounds 2a–c with Ac₂O/Py on heating rearranged to give 3a–c as major products and 4a–c as the minor products.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–5*

Compd. no.	M.p.** °C	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹
2a	170 ^a	—
b	194 ^b	—
c	192 ^a	—
3a	180 ^b	1 750 (C=O)
b	203 ^a	1 740 (C=O)
c	190 ^c	1 760 (C=O)
4a	255 ^d	1 750 (C=O of COCH ₃), 1 670 (C=O of lactone)
b	221 ^d	1 720 (C=O of COOH), 1 685 (C=O of lactone)
c	220 ^d	1 760 (C=O of COOH), 1 720 (C=O of lactone)
5a	158 ^d	—
b	208 ^d	—
c	191 ^d	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aCHCl₃, ^bEtOH, ^cMeOH, ^dEtOAc.

The compounds 2a–c and 4a–c on heating with aqueous NaOH gave one and the same compounds 5a–c due to hydrolytic cleavage of the lactone or anhydride ring as the case may be, followed by decarboxylation in case where the resulting compound is β -ketocarboxylic acid. Compound 5a–c underwent cyclodehydration by keeping them with concentrated H₂SO₄ overnight (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Reagents ; (i) Ac₂O/Py, room temp., (ii) Ac₂O/Py, 100°, (iii) aqueous NaOH, (iv) conc. H₂SO₄ and (v) RNH₂

The formation of 3a–c proceeded though pyridine catalysed acetylation of -CH₂- of the acid anhydride of the acids 1a–c formed *in situ* by action of Ac₂O. The reaction took place through the carbanion intermediate formed by the abstraction of

proton from CH₃, the high acidity of which is due to interposition between HOOC and C=C-COOH. The diones (2a-c) formed rearranged to give 3a-c. The similar type of reactions were studied on homophthalic acids, and 2-carboxyindole-3-acetic acid giving isocoumarins^{3,4} and pyrano[3,4-*b*]-indol-1-ones⁵.

Structures of the compounds were established from spectral data. Thus 3c gave nmr signals at δ (CDCl₃) 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.7 (1H, s, H-4) and 7.3-8.85 (6H, m, ArH). The methyl ester of 4c gave nmr signals at δ (DMSO) 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, COOCH₃) and 7.3-8.8 (6H, m, ArH). 3a gave nmr signals at δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-7), 2.75 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-3), 6.4 (1H, s, H-4) and 6.9-7.6 (3H, m, ArH).

The diones (2a-c) as well as the acids (4a-c) on heating separately with ammonia, aliphatic amines or aromatic amines gave *N*-substituted-3-methylbenzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridin-1-ones (6a-1 to 5a-3), 4-carboxy-3-methylnaphtho[2',3' : 5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyridin-1-ones (6b-1 to 6b-5) and 3-methylnaphtho[1',2' : 5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyridin-1-ones (6c-1 to 6c-7) respectively (Table 2), thus furnishing a good route for the synthesis of benzofuropyridinones and naphthofuropyridinones. The formation of 6a-c finds support from isoquinolones⁸ and β-carbolinones^{4,6}, prepared from isocoumarins and pyrano[3,4-*b*]indol-1-ones by the action of ammonia, aliphatic and aromatic amines.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6a-1 TO 6c-7*

Compd. no.	R ₄	R ₅	M.p.** °C	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹
6a-1	H	H	300 ^a	1 680 (C=O)
6a-2	Me	H	261 ^a	—
6a-3	Et	H	252 ^a	—
6b-1	H	COOH	300 ^b	1 780 (C=O of COOH), 1 480 (C=O of lactam)
6b-2	Me	COOH	230 ^c	1 720 (C=O of COOH), 1 680 (C=O of lactam)
6b-3	Pr	COOH	238 ^c	1 840 (C=O of COOH), 1 800 (C=O of lactam)
6c-1	H	H	200 ^a	1 770 (C=O of lactam)
6c-2	Me	H	202 ^a	1 770 (C=O of lactam)
6c-3	Et	H	204 ^a	—
6c-4	Pr	H	200 ^a	1 760 (C=O of lactam)
6b-4	Ph	H	273 ^d	—
6b-5	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	H	261 ^d	—
6b-6	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	H	248 ^d	—
6c-5	Ph	H	218 ^b	—
6c-6	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	H	215 ^a	—
6c-7	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	H	245 ^a	—

*For a, R₁=R₃=H, R₂=Me; b, R₁=H, R₂=R₃=Ph; c, R₁=R₂=Ph, R₃=H; all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis. ** Solvent for crystallisation: ^aC₆H₆, ^bAcOH, ^cMeOH, ^dEtOAc

Structures of 6a-c were established from its spectra. (6a-1) gave nmr signals at δ (COCl₂) 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-7), 2.32 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-3), 6.9-7.7 (4H, m, C-4 and ArH) and 11.3 (1H, s, NH). 6c-1 gave signals at δ 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.65 (1H, s, C-4), 6.7 (1H, s, NH) and 7.3-8.85 (6H, m, ArH). Mass spectrum of 6b-1 gave *m/z* 294.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a Varian A-60 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard.

Preparation of 2a-c. General procedure: The acid (1; 1 g) was added slowly to a mixture of acetic anhydride (4 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) with stirring at room temperature and the solution was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The solid separated was stirred with ether and separated.

Preparation of 3a-c: The reaction mixture was prepared as above and then heated on a boiling water-bath for 3 h. It was then diluted with ice-water and HCl when a black solid separated out. It was triaturated with aqueous NaHCO₃ and filtered. The insoluble residue was crystallised as 3a-c. The aqueous NaHCO₃ on acidification gave 4a-c which was filtered and crystallised. Methyl esters were prepared by heating 4a-c with methanol and concentrated H₂SO₄ for 16 h.

Preparation of 5a-c: 2a-c or 4a-c (0.5 g) was refluxed with aqueous NaOH (20 ml; 10%) for 3 h, then cooled and acidified with concentrated HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised.

Preparation of 6a-c: 2a-c or 4a-c (1 g) was refluxed with ammonia (30 ml), primary amine (15 ml) or aromatic amine (5 g) for 3 h. The product was either separated on cooling or by acidification with concentrated HCl and washed with water, dried and crystallised.

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